

Virtual Laboratory Strategies For Geometry And The Academic Performance Of Students

Francis I. Ogosi (PhD)¹; Florence E. Omonzejele (PhD)²; Francis E. Andem (Ph)³; Rupert A. Inwang⁴ & Assoc. Prof. Samuel Etuk⁵

^{1,2}Department of Business Administration
Western Delta University, Oghara, Nigeria

³Department of Business Administration & Management
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Nigeria

^{4,5}Department of Marketing
University of Uyo, Nigeria

¹Email: francis.ogosi@wdu.edu.ng/ Orcid ID:0000-0002-3892-4175 (Corresponding Author)

²Email: florence.omozejele@wdu.edu.ng/Orcid ID:0009-0002-2500-6962

³Email:francis.andem@akwaibompoly.edu.ng/Orcid ID:0000-0001-7713-3571

⁴Email: aniekaninwang.phd@uniuyo.edu.ng/Orcid ID:0009-0004-5320-6093

⁵asametuk@uniuyo.edu.ng/Orcid ID:0009-0004-5320-6093

ABSTRACT

This research study is on virtual laboratory strategies and the teaching of geometry to enhance the academic performance of students. The study's primary goal was to investigate the effect of virtual laboratory strategies in teaching geometry to enhance student's academic performance in the Nigerian state of Akwa Ibom, Uyo local government area. The survey research design was employed. The researcher made usage of primary data obtained from Senior Secondary II students of three public schools located in the Nigerian state of Akwa Ibom's Uyo local government area. The sample size (60 students) of the research study was determined via Taro Yamane's sampling technique. The linear regression method was used for analysing the data obtained from the survey conducted. The results showed that all the virtual laboratory strategies (Geogebra, Photomath and Mathway Applications) exhibited a strong effect on the academic performance of students in Geometry. The study concludes that Geogebra, Photomath and Mathway applications are strategic means of boosting the student academic performance in geometry. The researcher recommends that virtual laboratory applications be adopted by schools as strategic means in enhancing the student's academic performance in Geometry.

Keywords: Virtual Laboratory; Geogebra Application; Photomath Application; Mathway Application; Geometry; Academic Performance

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Since it encompasses so many different sub-learning areas, mathematics is a discipline that most students find challenging. Making mathematics teaching processes enjoyable and organizing teaching procedures through the use of various teaching methods, strategies, or resources has become essential in this regard. One of such teaching techniques is the use of virtual laboratory strategy in teaching some difficult mathematical concepts such as Geometry, Algebra, Trigonometry etc. This will give students the opportunity to learn these concepts by doing and provide them with intriguing and enjoyable activities that will make the lessons fun.

Utilizing virtual laboratories as a teaching strategy in mathematics is crucial for providing students with opportunities for trial and error, enabling them to form hypotheses, test them, and draw conclusions from the data by viewing themselves as mathematicians who make discoveries. A virtual laboratory is an interactive setup designed to create and run experiments using simulated tools (Ityavzua, 2019). When it comes to the several mathematics sub-learning areas, geometry is thought to be the most important one where students can engage in these kinds of trial-and-error exercises (Celen, 2020; Mazana *et al.*, 2019). Because of its abstract conceptual structure and demand for advanced thinking abilities from the learner, geometry is a challenging subject to study. Celen (2020) asserts that a student can only develop high-level learning skills in a subject if they are engaged in the activities included in the teaching process. It is evident that using virtual laboratories as a strategic approach to teaching mathematics will be successful in piquing students' interest in geometry instruction.

The significant absence of virtual laboratories in geometry education has dire consequences for the academic achievement of public secondary school pupils in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. These consequences include reduced engagement and interest, limited conceptual understanding, skill gaps in practical geometry and hindered technological proficiency.

As by SpriggHR (2023), an organization can be said to be planning whenever it sets a goal and allocates the necessary resources to accomplish it. A solid plan should be well-defined, covering all of the desired outcomes, without sacrificing any important details. It is more important to focus on long-term success than on quick achievement. According to SpriggHR (2023), applying strength against the most attractive opportunity is the fundamental principle of strategy. A good plan aims to develop strength as well as leverage what already exists. This is the point at which strategy is needed. The idea that strategy is the process of building strength serves to highlight the close relationship between strategy and tactics. Particular tactics are selected during strategy execution in order to strengthen and gain momentum in support of the strategic goal.

This refers, in this case, to the particular steps that educational establishments take to carry out the plans mentioned in the strategy. With regards to this research, the teaching of students with the aid of virtual laboratory strategies (Geogebra app, Photomath app and Mathway app) is the tactics being employed as a strategic method of increasing the performance of students in the area of geometry in mathematics. Geogebra app, Photomath app and Mathway app are all virtual laboratory educational applications that use technology to help users learn mathematics. Geogebra is a free, open-source app that allows users to create and manipulate interactive graphics to explore mathematical concepts. Photomath is a mobile app that via which users can scan and solve mathematical equations. Mathway is another mobile app that provides step-by-step explanations for solving math problems. All three apps are available for both iOS and Android devices. Geogebra, Photomath, and Mathway are all educational apps that can serve as valuable strategies to improve the geometry scores of secondary school students.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In an ideal scenario, geometry teachers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria's public secondary schools would have access to state-of-the-art virtual laboratories. Students might conceptualize and experiment with geometric concepts in a three-dimensional virtual environment with the help of these virtual laboratories, which would provide a wide range of immersive and interactive learning experiences. In a perfect world, qualified educators would also effortlessly incorporate virtual laboratory resources into their lesson plans to make geometry instruction interesting, useful, and applicable.

Regrettably, the current situation in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria reveals a significant absence of virtual laboratories in teaching geometry to public secondary school students. The majority of schools in the state lack access to such technological resources due to budgetary constraints, limited infrastructure, and inadequate training for teachers. Consequently, students are predominantly exposed to traditional, theoretical approaches to geometry, which may fail to capture their interest and hinder their ability to grasp complex concepts effectively.

Research on the use of virtual laboratories and their effects on improving geometry performance in public secondary school pupils in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, is essential in light of these grave repercussions. Such research can shed light on the potential benefits, challenges, and strategies for integrating virtual laboratories effectively into the educational system, ultimately paving the way for evidence-based educational reforms and improved academic outcomes in geometry education.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of the research is to ascertain the potential effect of virtual laboratory techniques on geometry education on the academic achievement of students in the Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The precise goals are:

- i. To assess the effect of Geogebra application as a virtual laboratory strategy on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the influence of Photomath application as a virtual laboratory strategy on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- iii. To investigate the effect of Mathway application as a virtual laboratory strategy on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

In line with the outlined objectives, some research questions are raised:

5. What is the effect of Geogebra application on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
6. What is the influence of the Photomath application on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
7. What is the effect of Mathway application on the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

In line with the objectives of the study, the null hypotheses to be tested are:

H₀₁: Geogebra application does not significantly affect the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Photomath application does not significantly influence the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Mathway application does not significantly affect the academic performance of students in geometry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study scope is narrowed down to three virtual laboratory proxies (Geogebra, Photomath and Mathway applications) while target study locations were three public secondary schools in Uyo Akwa Ibom State. 60 senior secondary two (SS2) students were utilised as the sample size for the research study. The proxies for virtual laboratory strategies were restricted to Geogebra, Photomath and Mathway applications respectively. The number of participating schools and students was limited by practical constraints.

2.0 Literature Review
2.1 Conceptual Review

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study
Source: Researcher’s Conceptualization (2024)

Figure 1 shows the conceptual foundation for the study in visual form. When teaching and learning geometry in mathematics, the employment of virtual laboratory strategies like Mathway, GeoGebra, and Photomath improves student comprehension and helps students perform better academically (Ghanem and Yahya, 2022).

2.1.1 Virtual Laboratory Strategy

It is impossible to overstate the critical functions that virtual laboratories play in real-world classroom exercises for laboratory-based courses. The widespread use of virtual laboratories in education can be attributed to the introduction of new technology gadgets such as laptops, iPads, tablets, and other Android phones, which pique students' interest when they use them. The design and development of virtual reality tools and facilities, which have the potential to improve practical activities in the classroom and beyond, have been made possible by the strategic use of these technologies in education. Additionally, these technological tools offer calculated chances to regulate or completely eradicate remote learning from classrooms in order to facilitate efficient or significant learning. Strategically, virtual laboratories can also help teachers improve the way they teach and help students improve the way they learn because they are computer-based learning tools that have been shown to boost students' interest in learning, which in turn makes it easier for them to design experiments and comprehend challenging concepts, particularly in the area of geometry.

Because virtual mathematics laboratories have advantages over traditional mathematics laboratories in terms of cost and accessibility, the strategic use of these resources for teaching and learning mathematics may result in a noticeable increase in students' interest in mathematics, particularly in geometry.

2.1.2 Geogebra Application

In secondary schools, the interactive computer program GeoGebra has been essential in the teaching and learning of geometry. When students interact with the interactive elements of the software, such as learning from feedback, recognizing patterns, drawing connections, and working with dynamic graphics, GeoGebra offers a platform for higher order thinking, especially for teachers (Adelabu *et al.*, 2019).

According to Adelabu *et al.* (2019), the application software offers a wide range of mathematical topics, including calculus, 3-D modeling, algebra, and geometry building. GeoGebra can be utilized with digital gadgets like tablets and interactive whiteboards. The computer program GeoGebra promotes the use of different representations, including tables, graphs, and equations. Stated differently, GeoGebra presents algebraic, numerical, and graphical depictions of mathematical objects on a single screen, with the graph shown in the graphic mode. As a result, several representations of the same item are combined dynamically, and any changes made to one of them instantly affect the others. Points, vectors, segments, polygons, straight lines, all conic sections, and functions in x are the fundamental objects in GeoGebra. Dynamic structures can be carried out with GeoGebra in the same way as with any other DGCS (Adelabu

et al., 2019). Both differentiated instruction and the flipped classroom could be implemented with this software. Additionally, it enhances the professional growth of educators by helping them create lesson plans that can serve as instruments for collaboration and illustration. Zulnaldi and Zamri (2017) state that Hohenwarter and Yves Kreis created the software in 2001, combining several mathematical trends into a single, user-friendly, open-source program. The presented graphic image of the GeoGebra application is seen in Figure 2.

Fig 2: Displayed graphic view of GeoGebra application
Source: Adelabu *et al.* (2019)

Previous research studies have shown that GeoGebra computer software in teaching mathematics contents is more effective than the conventional teaching that is pencil and paper (Zulnaldi and Zamri, 2017). Zengin *et al.* (2012) deduced in their research that the use of GeoGebra is more effective on learners' learning than conventional method in mathematics education. Selvy *et al.* (2016), affirms that GeoGebra computer software enhances the understanding of students about geometry which in turn leads to high academic performance in mathematics. The use of Geogebra also motivates and creates interest in the students to learn geometry and other mathematical concepts. Furthermore, Adegoke (2016) in his research study outcome concluded that incorporating GeoGebra in learning geometry and other mathematical concepts improves learning outcomes and academic performance of students. The findings of Dijanic and Trupevic (2017) in addition showed that virtual laboratory strategy by using Geogebra computer software interactive applets in mathematics teaching had certain perspectives which resulted in better acquisition of both procedural and conceptual knowledge than conventional teaching of mathematics.

2.1.3 Photomath Application

One program that can solve mathematical puzzles from texts is called Photomath; all it takes is capturing an image to use it. It includes step-by-step directions in addition to the solution. Numerous studies have demonstrated the beneficial effects of Photomath on mathematics learning. According to Saundarajan *et al.* (2020), students' learning of algebraic equations is improved by using the Photomath application. In

their pilot study, students achieved significantly better results when Photomath was used throughout the learning process. After introducing Photomath to the students, another study by Amparo *et al.* (2022) demonstrated an improvement in the learning outcomes of the students. The pupils also expressed optimism about using Photomath to increase their mathematical knowledge. Based on student feedback, Igcasama *et al.* (2020) also found that Photomath made math problem solving easy for everybody. The pupils also mentioned that Photomath offers an easy-to-use, aesthetically pleasing computational assistance tool. Several studies raise concerns regarding students using Photomath as a cheating tool for their class assignments, despite the favorable attitudes around its use. Professors fear, however, that this software may weaken students' ability to solve mathematical issues and think critically, which could lead to students shunning the role of math professors in imparting knowledge and providing guidance on mathematical problem-solving techniques. Boling and Gray (2021) addressed the problem of possible photomath cheating in students' assignments. Boling and Gray (2021) stated that teachers must find strategies to address the critical problem of Photomath being used as a cheating tool while directing students' tool use. Teachers may decide to ban virtual laboratories, restrict their use, or use them to revisit learning goals when more solutions become available. Boling and Gray (2021) also suggested that as an approach for raising kids' arithmetic skills, pupils should be taught more than what Photomath could provide. Educators can accomplish this by utilizing Photomath as a technique to evaluate students' mathematical flexibility. One method to allay worries about an application like Photomath and to evolve this kind of tool to keep up with the advancements in the modern learning environment is to respond to its existence.

Drawing on extant literature, including Hamadneh (2015) and Korenova and Veress-Bágyi (2018), it may be inferred that educators and learners alike hold a favourable view of Photomath's beneficial impact on students' academic achievement. According to Klara *et al.* (2021), German students primarily utilized Photomath to solve assignments and study for exams. They also reported an excessively positive attitude about the app's use in terms of improving their geometry knowledge. According to a Jordanian study that asked instructors about their opinions of the program, Hamadneh (2015) discovered a correlation between teachers' acceptance of using Photomath and their educational background. Greater education level was associated with noticeably more support. Although Korenová and VeressBágyi (2018) found that most people had a positive opinion of Photomath, they also thought that there was potential for improvement because similar virtual laboratory tactics may benefit students more broadly than what is being done in Central Europe.

2.1.4 Mathway Application

Numerous earlier researches revealed that pupils' academic achievement was generally low and their proficiency in mathematics in particular. Additionally, low academic achievement and low enthusiasm among pupils to learn mathematics are observed by educational researchers. Furthermore, a number of math teachers continue to insist on teaching mathematics using antiquated techniques without utilizing contemporary tools that enable students to participate actively in the learning process, effectively address issues facing education, and lessen student variability. Using virtual laboratory techniques like Mathway into the teaching and learning processes is one way to address these issues.

Ghanem and Yahya (2022) state that Mathway provides more than 400 topics, all of which are organized in an understandable and straightforward manner. These topics include pre-algebra, algebra, trigonometry, calculus, and linear algebra. Since the themes in each of these categories are related to the student's area of expertise, they can arrive at the solution more quickly. With Mathway, students may solve any number of problems. Over 1.3 billion problems were resolved for students using Mathway in 2019 (Ford and Boxser, 2020).

Mathway is an application that is used to answer mathematical issues in many domains. The issue is manually entered or captured with a picture, after which it is promptly resolved (Al-Bado, 2017). It is characterized procedurally as an app that can be downloaded into smart devices that teaches and clarifies the concepts of the Mathematics unit on relations and functions using algebra. According to Ghanem and Yahya's (2022) excerpts, Mathway is a web-based tool that students can use to solve a variety of mathematical issues. It is regarded as the most effective way for students to solve math problems and

enhance their performance in mathematics classes. Numerous areas of mathematics are covered, including algebra, trigonometry, calculus, linear algebra, statistics, graphs, and more.

Students can use Mathway to solve specific mathematical problems by just writing down the problem or taking a photo of it to receive a free, quick solution. Mathway offers students immediate assistance anywhere and at any time, with the option to subscribe for a fee in order to receive step-by-step solutions (Ghanem and Yahya, 2022). Similar to other virtual laboratory approaches in mathematics across many operating systems, the Mathway program is distinguished by a number of characteristics that facilitate and improve the learning process. These characteristics result from the benefits of adopting smart gadgets for learning as well as Thiagarajan's (2020) key points, which are:

1. Smart gadgets Students can access mathematical apps at any time and from any location; they are inexpensive, easy to use, and convenient to handle. Additionally, they promptly give pupils feedback.
2. Because mathematical problems are provided through smart device applications, these virtual laboratory tactics make students more successful and engage them in the learning process. These are digital platforms that trick the learner into viewing them as amusement apps or video games rather than schoolwork. This prompts him to focus on his education.

In addition to the aforementioned benefits, using virtual laboratory methodologies in general and Mathway in particular teaches students self-learning techniques and helps them become more independent, as confirmed by Ghanem and Yahya (2022). By using this kind of technology into the classroom, it helps the student become independent and helps them get past the challenges of algebra and mathematics. Additionally, it gives kids confidence and dispels their fear of mathematics by empowering them to know that they can solve any mathematical issue they come across. Additionally, the program assists students in identifying their areas of weakness.

2.1.5 Geometry

Geometry is the study of the relationships between points, lines, angles, surfaces, and solids, according to Buchori *et al.* (2023). The relationship between points, lines, angles, planes, and spatial forms is the subject of geometry. The study of the complexities of flat forms and shapes is known as geometry in mathematics. An organized approach to learning geometry begins with the foundational ideas referred to as basic conceptions. These form the basis for increasingly intricate parts that require explicit definitions, which are developed from the basic understanding. Axioms, also known as postulates, are deliberately constructed presumptions that are accepted as true without the need for explicit evidence. These axioms serve as the foundation for additional research and development in geometry, along with preexisting ones and their derivations. (Buchori, *et al.*, 2023).

Examining the subject of spatial thinking is quite interesting because previous studies have shown that children have difficulty understanding geometric objects or figures. According to Uttal *et al.* (2013), spatial thinking is a conglomeration of cognitive abilities made up of three parts: reasoning processes, representational tools, and spatial concepts. Within spatial thinking is the idea of spatial learning outcomes. Three categories—spatial perception, mental rotation, and spatial visualization—can be used to group the results of spatial learning. The results of the subsequent studies by Lowrie and Logan (2023) and Burte *et al.* (2020) indicate that improving spatial student achievement is crucial in the context of mathematics, especially geometry. As such, each student should strive to develop learning outcomes and spatial sensing, which are highly beneficial in comprehending geometry's relations and properties in order to solve mathematical problems as well as problems in daily life (Buchori *et al.*, 2023).

Despite geometry's place in Nigeria's secondary school general mathematics curriculum and its significance for other areas of study and other fields of mathematics (Ityavzua, 2019). It has been noted that one of the more challenging areas of mathematics for both teachers and students to acquire is geometry. This suggests that there has been a major problem with geometry instruction in Nigerian secondary schools recently. Olagunju and Jimoh (2013) and Ityavzua (2019) have also noted that there are still issues with geometry instruction and student performance in secondary schools in Nigeria. Consequently, investigating the issues impeding the successful teaching and learning of geometry in Nigerian secondary schools is crucial. It's crucial to look for creative approaches to geometry instruction in secondary schools in Nigeria. It is thought that incorporating virtual laboratory techniques into math

instruction can boost students' enthusiasm for geometry and ultimately improve their academic achievement. This is due to the fact that a pupil is more likely to succeed when they show interest in what they are doing.

2.1.6 Student Academic Performance

Any nation's development and growth are largely dependent on mathematics. This is accurate since scientific breakthroughs and technical advances—which are the real measures of a developed economy in any country—require a working knowledge of mathematics (Anigbo, 2016). According to research findings, mathematics is a crucial instrument for scientific and technical advancements that have helped many countries establish sustainable economies (Ityavzua, 2019). Math is a tool for any success in science and technology, which are two separate but interrelated fields. It implies that through efficient mathematics instruction, any developing country, like Nigeria, has to advance both economically and scientifically. Nigeria, as a country, implicitly trusted that science and technology would save her from poverty, illiteracy, and disease—the three indicators of an underdeveloped economy in any country—in an effort to create this sustainable economy (Ityavzua, 2019).

Despite mathematics' place in Nigeria's national education policy, the Chief Examiners' report from the WAEC (West African Examinations Council) for the 2010–2016 examination period reveals a persistently low level of academic performance in the country's secondary school general mathematics examination (Ityavzua, 2019). According to WAEC statistics based on geopolitical zones in Nigeria for the 2014–2015 examination, candidates performed poorly academically in mathematics overall, especially in the North-Central geopolitical zone (excluding the Federal Capital Territory) compared to other zones. Eleje *et al.* (2020) cite an extraction of the WAEC chief examiner's report that also reveals these statistics. Other researchers, including Olagunju and Jimoh (2013), have also noted that pupils in Nigeria's different geopolitical zones have consistently performed poorly academically in general mathematics, especially in geometry. It has been concerning and worrisome how poorly pupils are performing academically in mathematics, particularly in geometry. If this condition is not addressed, it may limit, impede, or prevent some students from being admitted to postsecondary schools. This circumstance will have an impact on other academic fields in addition to mathematics instruction.

Numerous variables have been connected to and blamed to Nigerian pupils' poor academic performance in mathematics. Among these are the teachers' predominance in using the traditional teaching approach, which is essentially the "chalk and talk" method combined with textbooks. Mathematical phobia, students' lack of interest in the subject, low and poor retention, and gender-related concerns are other factors that may have contributed to the poor academic performance of the pupils. Further contributing factors include a lack of mathematics teachers, impatient and unprepared teachers, students' disinterest in mathematics, the subject's abstract nature, the use of ineffective teaching strategies, students' inadequate mathematical backgrounds, and the absence of virtual mathematics laboratories in secondary schools in Nigeria (Ityavzua, 2019). Numerous researchers have noted that one of the main factors impeding effective mathematics teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools is the absence of a virtual mathematics laboratory, which ultimately contributes to students' subpar academic performance in mathematics, particularly in geometry.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

For the basis of this study, only the Cognitive Load Theory and the Constructivist Learning Theory were considered.

2.1.1 Cognitive Load Theory

Aygil and Meral (2012) state that John Sweller first introduced the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) in 1988. According to this idea, the cognitive burden placed on pupils' working memory during the learning process has an impact on learning. Working memory has limited capacity, and when learners are presented with complex information, they may become overwhelmed, leading to reduced learning outcomes. Virtual laboratories, which often involve interactive and multimedia elements, can increase cognitive load as students need to process both the instructional information and the technical aspects of using the virtual environment. In ways that traditional labs might not be able to, virtual laboratories can

provide students a more dynamic and engaging learning environment by letting them explore and engage with concepts. They can simulate real-life scenarios and support inquiry-based learning, enabling students to make connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications. On the other hand, the use of virtual laboratories can overwhelm students with excessive cognitive load due to the complexities of navigating the interface, managing technical issues, and processing the instructional content simultaneously. As a result, some students may struggle to effectively process and integrate the knowledge, leading to potential performance issues.

Implications of John Sweller's theory of Cognitive Load are:

- I. It implies that students have finite cognitive resources and that learning might be impeded by an excessive amount of cognitive load.
- II. It reduces the impact of split attention. When students are required to mentally integrate information delivered in disparate formats or locations, split attention arises

2.1.2 Constructivist Learning Theory

On the authority of WGU (2020), the Constructivist Learning Theory was propounded by Jean Piaget in 1972. The Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes that students actively construct their knowledge by interacting with their environment and assimilating new information into their existing mental frameworks. Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky were influential proponents of this theory. In the context of virtual laboratories, students have the opportunity to explore, manipulate, and interact with virtual objects and data, fostering active learning experiences. Virtual laboratories align well with constructivist principles, as they encourage students to take an active role in their learning. Students can engage in hands-on activities, conduct virtual experiments, and observe outcomes, which helps them build their understanding of scientific concepts. Additionally, virtual labs can cater to individual learning preferences and paces, supporting personalized learning experiences. However, while virtual laboratories offer valuable opportunities for constructivist learning, their effectiveness may be influenced by the quality of instructional design and the level of student engagement. If the virtual environment lacks interactivity, fails to challenge students, or does not provide appropriate scaffolding, the learning benefits may be limited.

Implications of the Jean Piaget's Constructivist Learning Theory are:

- I. Piaget's theory emphasizes that children construct knowledge actively through interactions with their environment.
- II. Piaget's theory highlights the importance of scaffolding – providing appropriate support and guidance to learners as they progress through their cognitive development.

Both theories provide valuable insights into understanding how virtual laboratories affect students' learning experiences, and educators should consider these factors when integrating virtual labs into the curriculum.

2.3 Empirical Study Reviews

Amalia *et al.* (2023) used PICOS (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design) to examine how students self-regulatedly learned (SRL) when using the Virtual Laboratory Strategy. They investigated whether using the Virtual Laboratory Strategy led to an increase in the SRL strategies—such as cognitive, metacognitive, motivational, behavioral, and contextual strategies—owned by students in higher education. After identifying 267 publications from the Web of Science and Scopus databases, 249 eligible papers were determined using the PRISMA principles. Out of all the articles, only twenty were deemed feasible based on four criteria: (1) higher education level; (2) providing information about online learning; (3) including materials about Virtual Laboratory; and (4) illustrating the idea of SRL. Nonetheless, the results demonstrated that every Virtual Laboratory Strategy had improved students' performance. Virtual Laboratory Strategies, which bridge the gap between students' past knowledge and experience and create an active social experience, might be chosen for giving the learning experience based on the data that has been analysed.

A quantitative, descriptive-comparative research approach was employed by Neil *et al.* (2023) to ascertain the extent of AI-PCA (Mathway app) utilization in math summative evaluations. Using stratified sampling, 50 respondents were chosen, and they were contacted using Google Forms to complete the

online survey questionnaires. The majority of the respondents were first-year students, while the minority was from the second year. Additionally, a higher percentage of responders were enrolled in online courses than in traditional classroom settings. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to examine the collected data. Regardless of their year level or preferred mode of instruction, the results showed that mathematics majors at a Catholic university displayed a high usage of the AI-PCA (Mathway app) in math summative assessments and academic dishonesty in distance learning. These indicators included various mathematics topics, activities, and student achievement motives. These results suggested developing a set of guidelines for the AI-PCA (Mathway app) in the classroom that would involve the subject area coordinator for mathematics, math teachers, and students.

Buchori *et al.* (2023) conducted research at the Universitas PGRI, Semarang, and the Universiti Teknologi, Malaysia, on the development of virtual laboratory geometry as an alternative to online learning medium. The research used the ADDIE paradigm, which is divided into five phases: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The result of the research is a virtual geometry lab. In this study, participants were students from two different universities: Universiti Teknologi, Malaysia, and the University of PGRI, Semarang. Each participant took two experimental classes and one control class. Following a pre- and post-test, answers were gathered via a questionnaire. Based on student feedback, up to 96% concurred that using a virtual media geometry lab can improve students' spatial and cognitive skills.

In order to assist five form two pupils in improving their math proficiency, particularly in factoring and algebraic development, Iffah *et al.* (2023) carried out an action research study. Five pupils with poor pre-test scores made up the study sample. Five secondary school students were included in the purposive sample used to choose research participants. Researchers can use the Photomath program to enhance teaching and learning processes through this action study. Pre-, post-, and observational data were gathered for this investigation, along with questionnaire data. After that, the data was evaluated to determine its frequency and percentage. The results of the post-test for the five respondents show an increase in math achievement and more interest in math subjects when they can refer to Photomath application based on the calculations they have done. The use of this application can be widely used as a tool to help students when they are at home and do not have a reference to refer to. The implications of this study show an increase in the respondents' achievement and interest in algebra.

The Photomath mobile application was examined by Amparo *et al.* (2022) as a teaching aid for algebra during distance learning. A quasi-experimental pretest-posttest One Group design was used in the investigation. Students in Grade 10 at Misamis Oriental General Comprehensive High School are randomly chosen to be the respondents. Prior to beginning the intervention activity that incorporates Photomath into education, the participants are given the pre-test via Google Meeting. The intervention was followed by the post-test. The analysis's findings demonstrated that utilizing Photomath in the classroom significantly improved students' performance in mathematics. Researchers advise carrying out additional research on photomath integration in mathematics.

Ghanem and Yahya (2022) looked into how utilizing the Mathway application affected the growth of mathematic academic achievement in secondary school pupils in the city of Najran. All second-year secondary school students studying mathematics in Najran City made up the study population. A sample of 83 students was used in the study, which employed a quasi-experimental approach. Of these, 41 students studied using the Mathway application in the experimental group, and 42 students studied using the conventional manner in the control group. A pre-achievement test was created prior to the experiment to verify that the two groups are equal, and a post-achievement test was created to determine any discrepancies between the two groups following the experiment. The use of the Mathway application by the experimental group resulted in a statistically significant difference at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) amongst the means of the experiment group and those of the group used as a control in the post-academic achievement test. The study suggested employing the Mathway application and other comparable applications in the teaching and learning of mathematics in light of the findings.

The efficiency of the Mathway Application as a virtual laboratory technique in raising the performance of Piagapo National High School, Piagapo, Philippines, Grade 10 students in solving trigonometric problems was the main emphasis of Hadjinor et al.'s (2021) study. This study employed a quasi-experimental research design. The profile of the participants was characterized by their age, gender, and most recent math grade. Additionally, this study aimed to address the following: participant profiles with respect to age, gender, and most recent math grade; pre- and post-test participant test performance profiles; significant differences in test performance between pre- and post-test participants; and participant opinions regarding the use of Mathway application for trigonometry problem solving. After the pre-test was given, there was an intervention for three weeks. There was an intervention, and then a post-test. Analysis and interpretation were done on the test results from the pre- and post-test. The study's conclusions demonstrated a substantial difference in the students' performance between the pre- and post-tests, indicating that Mathway raised their performance levels. The participants also expressed agreement that using the Mathway application helped pupils become more proficient at solving trigonometric issues. Therefore, it is advised that educators use Mathway and other virtual laboratory techniques into their lesson plans.

Williams (2020) examined a variety of student-use software programs and websites, such as Mathway, Geogebra, Slader, Wolfram Alpha, Symbolab, Desmos, and Photomath. Next, the study looked into the motivations behind students' use of various websites and apps. There were nine students involved in the study. These kids were identified using questionnaires, and a phenomenological method was used for the interviews. After that, the data was examined using the Modified Van Kaam technique. With this approach, individual structural and textural descriptions as well as a composite group description have to be created. These interviews gave rise to several themes, including learning, easy access, and boosting confidence. The findings demonstrated that the majority of students defended their usage of websites and digital apps by claiming to be studying from them. Pupils believed that these things were resources for their education. The students in each instance did not believe they were plagiarizing. In order to enhance their academic achievement, students said they intended to keep using websites and digital apps to finish their arithmetic homework.

An evaluation of Photomath's use in teaching basic algebra was conducted by Igcasama *et al.* (2020). Its specific goal was to determine the impact of using Photomath in Elementary Algebra instruction. For the study, experimental, quantitative, and qualitative designs were used. This was done through two different sections of an Elementary Algebra teaching demo for Grade 7. A pre-test was given prior to the demo's execution, and a post-test followed the instructional demo. The findings of the section with Photomath as the intervention showed a substantial change between the pre- and post-tests, according to the study. Furthermore, the findings of the section with and without the aforementioned application as intervention showed an important distinction between the pre- and post-tests. It did, however, demonstrate that there was little variation between the two portions. The first segment demonstrated that using Photomath as a teaching tool had a beneficial impact on students' performance, but there was no discernible difference between it and the conventional teaching approach. This was probably caused by the study's short sample size; hence, it was advised to have more sample sizes to re-evaluate the effectiveness of Photomath vs the conventional approach to teaching elementary algebra. In summary, the study suggested that using Photomath as an educational instrument affected the way elementary algebra was taught.

The goal of Saundarajan, et al. (2020) was to ascertain how the Photomath mobile application affected Malaysian lower secondary school pupils' attitude and performance when learning algebraic equations. 33 lower secondary students' pre- and post-test results, along with questionnaire responses, were gathered. Pre- and post-test results were analyzed to look into how well students performed after using Photomath, while a questionnaire was employed to find out how students felt about using Photomath to learn algebraic equations in terms of belief and preparedness. The pre- and post-test mean scores were compared, and a t-test was utilized for hypothesis testing. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the questionnaire data. According to the study, using Photomath greatly improves pupils' understanding of algebraic equations. Nonetheless, the degree of belief and preparedness among the participants regarding Photomath remains minimal.

The impact of dynamic geometry computer software on geometry learners' performance was investigated by Adelabu et al. (2019). There was a non-equivalent, quasi-experimental control group. The geometry achievement maths test (GAMT), which has 15 multiple-choice items, was the tool employed in this investigation. In Tshwane South District, Gauteng Province, South Africa, two secondary schools hosted 87 students enrolled in grade nine, who were given the GAMT. The experimental group consisted of one school, while the control group was one other school. The independent sample of the statistical t-test was used in data analysis. The study's findings demonstrate the value of utilizing Geogebra in geometry classes, as it enhances students' performance. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the software has a greater favorable impact on the mathematics performance of female learners than male learners. Thus, the study's findings demonstrated the considerable potential of utilizing Geogebra in secondary mathematics instruction. According to the report, schools should prioritize integrating technology into their math instruction.

Gamage and Charles-Ogan (2019) looked into how well students performed when teaching and studying about circles using the Geogebra software. Two goals, two research questions, and two null hypotheses that were examined at .05 alpha levels served as the study's compass. For the study, a quasi-experimental research design including pre- and post-tests was used. The sample consisted of 117 senior secondary school students and 25,913 total students from the thirty-three public schools situated in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. The sample was chosen using the purposive sampling technique. The Geometry Performance Test (GPT) was the tool utilized to get the data. Using the test-retest procedure, a reliability index of .75 was determined for GPT performance. The data was analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, and covariance analysis. The outcome demonstrated that pupils in the experimental group, who were instructed in circle geometry utilizing Geogebra software, outperformed their peers in the control group, who received instruction using the conventional approach. The outcome additionally demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the average achievement of students taught circular geometry using Geogebra compared to students taught using the conventional approach. The average achievement of the male and female students who were taught circular geometry utilizing the Geogebra software did not differ significantly. It was determined that using Geogebra software instead of the conventional approach to teaching circle geometry enhanced student performance.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The survey research method was applied for this study which involved the use of questionnaire to obtain data from the sampled respondents.

3.2 Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The study's population consisted of SS2A students from three schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State: West Itam Secondary School, the community Secondary School the Uyo High School. Total population of the SS2A students from the three schools stood at 152. The study's schools were chosen using the convenience sampling approach, and the SS2A students—likely the best students—were chosen using the purposive sample method in order to obtain pertinent data for a methodical analysis. The sample size being 60 students was determined via the Taro Yamane's sample size determination technique.

3.3 Data Source and Data Analysis

Primarily, the data were gathered from original sources. Reliability tests were done to assess the questionnaire utilized for primary data collection, and the results showed a Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.728. The data acquired for the study were analyzed using the linear regression method of analysis.

3.4 Model Specification

The theories adopted for the study were the Cognitive Load Theory and the Constructivist Learning Theory. The theories suggest that the virtual lab strategies under study have a relationship with the teaching of geometry and can influence the academic performance of students in geometry.

The simple linear regression model was used to test all three null hypotheses (**Ho₁**, **Ho₂**, and **Ho₃**) by ascertaining the relationship of each independent variable with the dependent variable as represented below:

$$\text{SAPG} = f(\text{virtual laboratory strategy}) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$\text{SAPG} = X_0 + X_1\text{GG}_1 + \text{et} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$\text{SAPG} = X_0 + X_1\text{PHM}_1 + \text{et} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$\text{SAPG} = X_0 + X_1\text{MW}_1 + \text{et} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where SAPG = students’ academic performance in geometry, X_0 = intercept, X_1 = coefficient of the variables, GG_1 = geogebra, PHM_1 = photomath, MW_1 = mathway and et = stochastic term (error term).

The a priori expectation is $X_1 > 0$

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION.

The data collated from the questionnaire copies is analyzed in this section using the linear regression analysis.

In response to research question one, an assessment of the independent effect of Geogebra application on the student academic performance in geometry was carried out on the dependent variable (SAPG) using the simple linear regression analysis and the results were collated into Table 4.1

Table 4.1 Simple Linear Regression Result

Variable	Beta(β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio	Durbin-Watson
Constant	6.207	6.180	0.000	Significant				
GEO	0.560	9.399	0.000	Significant	0.604	0.597	88.344	2.476

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2024

Geogebra application usage returned an R square value of 0.604 which implies that 60.4 percent of the changes in the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area are affected by 60.4 percent of the changes in Geogebra application usage. The percentage figure shows that there are other factors concerning Geogebra application usage that affect the changes in the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area. The F-statistic of 88.344 and p-value showed that the model was significant and that there was a significant effect of Geogebra application usage on the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area. The t-statistic value of 9.399 alongside a p-value of 0.000 and beta value of 0.560 indicated that there is a positive and significant effect of Geogebra application usage on the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area. This indicates that Geogebra application usage is a strong determinant of the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area.

In response to research question two and H_{02} , the photomath app was regressed against the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government and the results are presented in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 Simple Linear Regression Result

Variable	Beta(β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio	Durbin-Watson
Constant	10.869	7.248	0.000	Significant				
PHO	0.275	3.100	0.003	Significant	0.142	0.127	9.612	1.644

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2024

Photomath application usage returned an R square value of 0.127 implying that 12.7 percent of the changes in the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State are affected by 12.7 percent of the changes in Photomath application usage. The F-statistic (9.612) and p-value showed that the model was significant and that a linear relationship exists between Photomath application usage and the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. The t-statistical outcome of 3.100 alongside the p-value of 0.003 showed that there is a significant and positive influence by Photomath application usage on the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that as Photomath application usage increases, the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State increases.

In response to research question three and H_{03} , the influence of the mathway application was determined by regressing against the student academic performance in Uyo local government area and the results are presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Simple Linear Regression Result

Variable	Beta(β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio	Durbin-Watson
Constant	8.530	7.101	0.000	Significant				
MAT	0.461	5.889	0.000	Significant	0.374	0.363	34.676	1.541

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2024

Mathway application usage returned an R square value of 0.374 implying that 37.4 percent of the changes in the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State were affected by the changes in Mathway application usage. The F-statistic (34.676) and p-value (0.000) showed that the model was significant and that a linear relationship existed between Mathway application usage and the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. The t-statistical outcome of 5.889 and beta-value outcome of 0.461 alongside the p-value of 0.000 showed that there was a significant effect by Mathway application usage on the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that as Mathway application usage increases, the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State significantly increases.

In line with the linear regression analysis outcome, there was a positive and significant effect by Geogebra application usage on the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. This result finding is in tandem with the works of Williams (2020), Gamage and Charles-Ogan (2019) then Adelabu, Makgato and Ramaligela (2019) where they showed that Geogebra application usage have a significant positive effect on the academic performance of students in Geometry. Photomath application usage on the other hand showed a positive statistically significant influence on the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State and this is in line with the studies of Iffah, et al. (2023); Amparo, et al. (2022) and Igcasama, Ramirez and Salanap (2020). Mathway application usage displayed a positive significant effect on the student academic performance in geometry in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. This result finding concurs with the outcomes of the research studies of Neil, et al. (2023), Ghanem and Yahya (2022) and Hadjinor, Asotigue and Pangandamun (2021), where they discovered that Mathway application usage displayed a positive significant effect towards the students’ academic performance in mathematics.

4.1 Policy Implication of Findings

The policy implications of these findings are that educational policies should be put in place to provide more support for students in using technology to improve their performance in geometry. Specifically, policies should:

- (i) Provide students with access to technology tools such as Mathway, Photomath, and Geogebra.
- (ii) Develop training programs for teachers to use these tools effectively in the classroom.
- (iii) Support students in using these tools responsibly and ethically.
- (iv) Continue to invest in research on the impact of technology on student learning.
- (v) Evaluate the effectiveness of these tools and adjust policies as needed.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Virtual laboratory strategies (measured by Geogebra application, Photomath application and Mathway application) were regressed against the dependent variable student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area. The findings revealed that all the Virtual laboratory strategies indicator measures significantly influenced the student academic performance in geometry within Uyo local government area. Based on these findings, the study concludes that the Geogebra, Photomath and Mathway applications are strategic means of boosting the student academic performance in geometry. Based on the findings, the study recommends for the incorporation of the use of Geogebra, Photomath

and Mathway applications into geometry instruction in Uyo Local Government Area schools. While these applications offer significant benefits, it's important to use them as supplements to traditional teaching methods rather than substitutes. Educators should encourage students to use these applications as aids for learning, problem-solving, and reinforcement of concepts. Additionally, promoting critical thinking and independent problem-solving skills is essential, such that students don't overly rely on the applications for answers but instead use them as tools for learning and growth. Finally, teachers should be trained on how to use these virtual laboratory applications effectively and make sure students are using them responsibly.

5.1 Contribution to Knowledge and Future Research

These findings add to the body of research on the use of technology in education, and provide evidence that these tools can be effective in helping students learn geometry. Furthermore, the findings highlight the importance of providing students with access to technology, training teachers on how to use it effectively, and developing policies that support its use in an ethical and responsible manner.

It is suggested that similar proxies for virtual laboratory strategies be researched against student performance in other subjects such as algebra, calculus, and statistics in other parts of Nigeria to have a holistic perspective of the varying disaggregated research findings as captured by researchers with regards to virtual laboratory strategies for various economies.

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